

**ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF SUMMER ACADEMIC REMEDIAL PROGRAM
AND THE LEARNING CAMP IN THE ACADEMIC SUCCESS OF LEARNERS****Josie Lyn C. Estrada**

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ABSTRACT

Academic remedial program is a continuing academic intervention that supports learning recovery of the learners and establish efficient instruction in bridging instructional gaps and learners' academic competence. This study explored the perceived effects of summer academic remedial program and the learning camp in the academic success of learners among selected public secondary schools in the Philippines. It employed a descriptive correlational research design. Researcher-made survey-questionnaire was used as the main research instrument. Thus, the study was participated by 300 randomly selected public secondary school teachers in the Philippines. Statistical tools were used such as mean, standard deviation and Pearson Correlation Coefficient in order to explore and examine the perceived effects of summer academic remedial program and the learning camp in the academic success of the learners Results revealed that teachers highly perceived that remedial program was an effective instructional intervention that supported learning development. Instruction and assessment techniques aspect were perceived by the teachers to be the most significant indicators that caused the effectiveness of the remedial program. On one hand, the study further concluded that teachers highly perceived that learning camp was an effective platform to plan, design, discuss and present instructional programs relative to the implementation of schools' remedial program. Hence, the study found out that was a moderate positive correlation on teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program in terms of instruction and their perceptions on the impact of national learning camp in the academic success of the learners in terms of plan and design of the lesson .Thus, the study recommended that comprehensive development of instructional program intervention should be created focusing on creative and innovative instructional designs to facilitate efficient remedial program.

Keywords:

Remedial, program, summer, learning, camp, instruction, assessment, plan, design

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine government strongly emphasizes the provision of quality-based education among Filipino learners. In the resurfacing educational settings, the Philippine educational system as operated by the national government's primary organ that implements, regulates and monitor the effective delivery of education among basic education institutions—the Department of Education. Apparently, one of the critical concerns of the department is the consistent provision of quality-based instruction, inclusive, relevant and responsive educational system that can directly help learners in their holistic development. Constitutional rights of the learners are strongly safeguarded by the state as they are to be accorded with the quality-based instruction resulting to quality education where they acquire effective and meaningful learning experiences. Learners' right to education does not end on the provision of proper educational system where they are provided wider repertoire of learning opportunities substantial for their total development. True and impactful education primarily surrounding basic education institutions' instructional processes, is the consistent provision of quality-based instruction whereas teaching and learning process are highly impactful and beneficial to the learners' needs, interests and readiness. Central focus of Philippine's basic education institutions specially the public

school system are the learners who are the main recipients of teaching and learning process. The quality of teaching and learning process compromising the totality of instructional processes is expected to be implemented with pure consistencies and responsive to the needs and interests of Filipino learners. While the national government is keen and responsive to the needs and future successes of learners through meaningful education, there are several conditions that create challenges and difficulty for teachers and learners obtain quality-based instruction. Apparently, one of the perennial educational problem which the Philippines experience to this time is the low level of academic performance of learners emanating from their poor academic performance inside the teaching and learning process. The results of several international assessment including the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) which shows that Filipino learners are at the dismal bottom ranking in english, science and mathematics. This results put greater concerns among teachers, policy-makers and all other concerned, at large, by the national government. This indicates that Filipino learners are significantly left behind when ranked to international and global standards in line with the academic competence of learners. Added to this, is the recent reports on Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM) which asserts that Filipino learners are extremely left behind in line with their academic performances. Further, the findings contained in the report show that Philippine basic education system immensely face educational problems which if not answered nor resolved, would inflict long-term damage to the country's educational system.

With the problems and challenges encountered by teachers, learners, school heads, department's officials and all other concerned individuals, Philippine education is confronted with the diversity of challenges which make teachers, school heads and department's officials bombarded and pressured. In this line, while the government identified these severe educational problems which part and parcel of such problems, is the poor academic performance of learners and the continued decline on the level of academic competence shown by Filipino learners in the basic education level. To this effect, the Department of Education (DepEd) is not silent but proactive and responsive to the continued development of programs that would help teachers, learners, parents and school officials to reduce the increasing academic-related problems encountered by the learners. Consequently, the department's commitment to significantly address the learning loss and closing the learning gaps in the basic education system. The enactment of summer programs and its implementation have been actively advanced by the department. Reasons behind the implementation of summer program is to support learners in strengthening their foundational knowledge and skills as they move forward in their education journey. As contained in the recent order as released by the department, reflecting under Department Order No. 10, s. 2025 which established the guidelines for the implementation of the 2025 Department of Education Summer Programs. Contained in this order are the structure of summer programs supporting the development of learners' academic performance. Thus, the reinforcement and continued cultivation of learners' academic competence are structured under three elements: (1) summer programs for key stage 1 under the Bawat Bata Makababasa Program, Literacy Remediation Program, (2) Summer Academic Remedial Program and Regional Remediation Program for key stages 2 to 4 and (3) 2025 Learning Camp. The program directly instituted the whole-of-community approach where it adhered to the cultivation, collaboration and partnerships with parents, encouraging teachers to work together and engage community partners to support learners' academic competence.

The implementation of summer academic remedial program as contained in the thrust of 2025 Department of Education Summer Programs is significantly viewed as an important mechanism in developing learners' academic competence. In this regard, the researchers directly observed that there are less number of scholarly studies that directly focused in analyzing the impact of summer remedial program on the academic success of learners. Also, prevailing conditions observed by the researchers are the presence of insufficient credible research works which may or may not assert the positive effects of summer remedial programs and learning camp. Apparently, the researchers also observed that there is also absence of empirical evidences that may substantiate the impact of summer academic remedial program and learning camp to learners' academic success. Bridging the achievement gap among learners and maximizing the effectiveness of instruction have attracted significant academic development of learners. Thus, remediation instruction significantly helped learners to cope with the academic challenges they encountered in a regular instructional processes (Al Ghaith and Behforouz, 2023). Meanwhile, learning camp is another form of the national government's initiative to ensure the competence of teachers to deliver meaningful and retentive instruction. In this regard, the researchers rise their interests in doing this study as they find less number of researches which directly focus in analyzing the impact of national learning camp as program intervention for the enhancement of teachers' teaching competence

hence, also geared towards the improvement of learning outcomes in the basic education system. The learning camp fosters collaboration, engagement and communication. Thus, it enabled teachers to provide more engaging, inclusive and achievable structure of learning activities for the total development of learners (Buendia, 2025). Centered on learning engagement, effectiveness of specific teaching methodologies such as group discussions and hands-on experiences formed the refinement and diversification of approaches to enhance the teaching and learning process (David et al., 2025). Learning camp and the summer academic remedial program are two significant academic intervention program enabling teachers to create highly engaging instructional process in the normal teaching and learning set-up (Ledesma, 2025).

OBJECTIVES

This study explored and examined the perceived impact of summer academic remedial program and the learning camp in the academic success of the learners among selected public secondary school teachers in the Philippines. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. examine teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program in terms of instruction, classroom management and assessment
2. examine teachers' perceptions on the impact of national learning camp in the academic success of the learners in terms of plan and design of the lesson, teaching strategies, creativity and innovation.
3. examine if there would be significant relationship between teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program and their perceived impact of national learning camp in the academic success of their learners.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program and their perceived impact of national learning camp in the academic success of their learners.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive correlational research design. The study selected the participation of 300 public secondary school teachers among selected public schools in the Philippines through the use of simple random sampling. Apparently, the study used a researcher-made survey-questionnaire which contained two (2) parts. For part 1, it contained items relating to the teachers' perceptions on the impact of academic remedial program and while for part 2, it contained items relating to the teachers' perceptions on the impact of national learning camp in the academic success of the learners. Thus, the researcher-made survey-questionnaire used a 4-Likert Scale such as: 4-strongly agree, 3-agree, 2-disagree and 1-strongly disagree. The researchers subjected the developed survey-questionnaire in validation and reliability test. Validation was done through the expertise of three (3) graduate school professors who have marked the developed survey-questionnaire as "outstanding." Apparently, the reliability results showed that items under part 1 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of $\alpha=.817$ while items under part 2 obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of $\alpha=.889$, which signified that the constructed items were acceptable. Meanwhile, in the actual collection of the data, the researchers designated two (2) enumerators who administered questionnaire. They used a Google Form link and sent to the respondents' email addresses. Meanwhile, the researchers used relevant statistical techniques where they used mean, standard deviation and general weighted mean in order to examine teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program and the impact of learning camp in the academic success of the learners. Thus, the researchers also used Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) in order to examine if there would be significant relationship between teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program and their perceived impact of national learning camp in the academic success of their learners. Apparently, the researchers also used informed consent and assent forms so as to comply with the highest ethical standards in doing an independent research study. Gathered data were stored on the researchers' personal devices. Similar stored data were deleted after the completion of this study. Anonymity was used in order to conceal the identities of the respondents and to abide with the pertinent provisions of Data Privacy Act.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analyzing the impact of summer academic remedial program and the learning camp is vital as it can provide empirical evidences in order to continually develop and modify the structure of the program based on the

prevailing needs and conditions encountered by teachers and learners. In this regard, academic success is an ultimate measure of positive impact of the implemented programs. This study is also of greater importance as it can be a reference in conducting further studies relative to the implications of summer academic remedial program and the national learning camp.

1. **Teachers' Perceptions on the Impact of Summer Academic Remedial Program in the Academic Success of Learners.** The results showed that instruction and assessment were highly perceived as the most significant impact extracted from the implementation of summer academic remedial program with a mean of 3.92, described as highly perceived while classroom management gained a mean of 3.21, described as perceived. The results implied that teachers highly perceived the summer academic remedial program as significant program helped them in developing their instructional practices and assessment techniques. Here, the results also revealed that the program effectively equipped learners and teachers with retentive and meaningful structure that directly supported learners in coping with the competencies which they found difficult. Apparently, the high mean scores obtained under these two variables indicated that teachers under the summer academic remedial program highly perceived that the same has instituted significant positive impact on learners' academic success and academic performance. Meanwhile, the results also indicated that teachers perceived that classroom management also positively impacted the academic success of their learners through the implementation of summer academic remedial program. This further indicated that teachers recognized some benefits of the program in the enhancement of their instructional practices which could be administered under their regular instructional processes. Notably, the high perception in instruction and assessment underscored that teachers felt that the program provided them wide teaching and learning opportunities that directly benefited their learners and so, their instructional practices specifically their teaching strategies and assessment techniques. Results of the study supported the study of Rai and Penjor (2020) which revealed that remedial program was an effective teaching and learning process, designed to address with the learners learning gaps and eventually, deepened their learnings. Similar study showed that remedial class was implemented in any instruction effectively influenced learners' competence. The study implicated that the program further needing improvements specially in considering the feedback from parents before, during and after the implementation of the program.
2. **Teachers' Perceptions on the Impact of National Learning Camp in the Academic Success of Learners.** The result showed that teachers highly perceived national learning camp to be a significant and effective platform to plan and design the lesson which gained the highest mean of 3.94, described as highly perceived. Meanwhile, the results showed that teachers perceived national learning camp as effective process in advancing their teaching strategies, creativity and innovation which obtained mean scores of 3.25, 3.18 and 3.22 respectively, all described as perceived. The results implied that teachers highly perceived the national learning camp as highly effective platform for planning and designing lessons. This further showed that teachers highly perceived the national learning camp to be valuable instructional avenue supporting their ability to create highly engaging lessons for their learners' academic success. Meanwhile, the results also revealed that teachers perceived national learning camp as beneficial for the advancement of their teaching strategies, creativity and innovation. Notably, this also indicated that national learning camp was recognized by teachers as effective instructional platform to construct and reconstruct their abilities in developing creative and innovative instruction for their learners' academic enhancement. The results also practically revealed that national learning camp became a platform for lesson planning underscoring its roles in the provision of structured instructional guidance and resources for teachers in the continued pursuit for academic excellence and success of their learners. Results of the study supported the study of Luana and Siat (2025) which revealed that teachers developed their instructional development techniques as they were exposed during the camp with the voluminous techniques and principles in making highly engaging lessons. The study implicated that teachers, school heads, learners and program implementers should collaborate and actively enhance the program's structure to directly respond with their academic needs. Thus, the program should be more contextual and localized so as to address other instructional and academic concerns faced by teachers and learners.
3. **Relationship Between Teachers' Level of Awareness and Technical Writing Skills in Developing an Application of Education Project.** The result showed that there was a moderate positive correlation on teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program in terms of

instruction and their perceptions on the impact of national learning camp in the academic success of the learners in terms of plan and design of the lesson ($r=.449$). This suggested that as teachers become more aware of and positively perceive the impact of summer academic remedial program and the national learning camp, their technical writing skills in instructional design also increases. The result further implied that when teachers recognized the value of these programs, they are more likely to create more comprehensive instructional content that could lead to the efficiency and effectivity of the delivery of instruction among their learners. Results of the study supported the study of Abad et al. (2025) which revealed that programs initiated by the national government such as the summer academic remedial program and the national learning camp imposed effective instructions that caused the increased on learners' academic achievement. The study implicated that there should be expanded professional development opportunities and learners' extended learning programs which could further solidified their academic success.

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CONCLUSION

Teachers highly perceived that remedial program was an effective instructional intervention that supported learning development. Instruction and assessment techniques aspect were perceived by the teachers to be the most significant indicators that caused the effectiveness of the remedial program. On one hand, the study further concluded that teachers highly perceived that learning camp was an effective platform to plan, design, discuss and present instructional programs relative to the implementation of schools' remedial program. Hence, the study found out that was a moderate positive correlation on teachers' perceptions on the impact of summer academic remedial program in terms of instruction and their perceptions on the impact of national learning camp in the academic success of the learners in terms of plan and design of the lesson. Thus, the study recommended that comprehensive development of instructional program intervention should be created focusing on creative and innovative instructional designs to facilitate efficient remedial program.

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